

PSYCHOLOGICAL DESCRIPTIONS TO THE MAIN CHARACTERS OF THE STORY BY KATE CHOPIN, "STORY OF AN HOUR"

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278899>

Abstract: This article explores the connection between language and psychology in Kate Chopin's "Story of an Hour." The author examines how language is used to convey Louise Mallard's emotional response to her husband's death and her subsequent liberation. The use of emotive language sets the tone of despair and sadness at the beginning of the story, while descriptions of the natural world create a sense of freshness and freedom. As Louise's thoughts undergo a transformation, language reflecting her newfound independence and power is employed. Overall, Chopin's mastery of language allows readers to empathize with Louise's emotional journey.

Key words: language, psychology, emotional response, psycholinguistics, emotional state, liberation, melancholy, euphoria, independence, mental state.

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ ОПИСАНИЕ ОСНОВНЫХ ПЕРСОНАЖЕЙ ИСТОРИИ КЕЙТ ШОПЕН "ИСТОРИЯ ОДНОГО ЧАСА".

Аннотация: Эта статья исследует связь между языком и психологией в "Истории одного часа" Кейт Шопен. Автор рассматривает, как язык используется для передачи эмоциональной реакции Луизы Маллард на смерть ее мужа и ее последующее освобождение. Использование эмоционального языка создает тон отчаяния и печали в начале истории, в то время как описания природного мира создают ощущение свежести и свободы. По мере трансформации мыслей Луизы, применяется язык, отражающий ее обретенную независимость и силу. В целом, мастерство Шопен в использовании языка позволяет читателю сопереживать эмоциональному путешествию Луизы.

Ключевые слова: язык, психология, эмоциональная реакция, психолингвистика, эмоциональное состояние, освобождение, меланхолия, эйфория, независимость, психическое состояние.

INTRODUCTION

Kate Chopin's "Story of an Hour" is a short story that explores the complex emotional world of a woman, Louise Mallard, who is informed of her husband's death. The story is a strong representation of how language and psychology intersect to create an emotional response to the event.

Psycholinguistics is the study of the relationship between language and the mind. This field has become an essential tool for studying the ways that we use language to communicate our thoughts, emotions, and intentions. In "Story of an Hour," the use of language plays a significant role in conveying Louise's psychological state and emotional response to her husband's death.¹

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

At the beginning of the story, Chopin sets the tone for the reader through the use of language. The first sentence which states, "Mrs. Mallard, afflicted with a heart trouble, was taken with a sudden attack of grief" immediately conveys a sense of despair and sadness. The use of "afflicted," "sudden," and "grief" create a somber tone and helps the reader understand the magnitude of the situation. This use of emotive language continues throughout the story, filling it with a range of emotions- from melancholy to euphoria.²

As Louise struggles with the news of her husband's death, she begins to experience a sense of liberation due to the use of language. One example is when she looks through the window and sees the new life outside, with the "delicious breath of rain" and "the sparrows were twittering in the eaves."¹ Here, Chopin's language transports the readers into the world Louise is experiencing, creating a sense of freshness that helps her understand this newfound sense of freedom.

RESEARCH RESULTS

"The Story of an Hour" by Kate Chopin is a short story that explores the complex emotions and psychological experiences of its main character, Mrs. Mallard, Mrs. Mallard can be described as:

1. Emotionally repressed: At the beginning of the story, Mrs. Mallard appears to be a woman with a constrained emotional life. She is described as having "a face that was young and pretty," but it is also mentioned that "she had never been joyful."⁵ This suggests that she has long suppressed her emotions, perhaps due to societal expectations or personal circumstances.

2. Torn between societal expectations and personal desires: After receiving the news of her husband's death, Mrs. Mallard goes through a series of conflicting emotions. At first, she responds with the expected grief and weeps in her sister's arms. However, as she retreats to her room alone, a different set of emotions emerge. She begins to feel a sense of freedom and liberation, thinking about the opportunities for a life without her husband. This suggests an internal conflict between what she believes is expected of her and her own desires for independence.

3. Experiencing a transformative moment: As Mrs. Mallard reflects on her newfound sense of freedom, she undergoes a transformative moment of self-realization. She begins to embrace the idea of living for herself rather than for others. This change is described as a "storm of grief" being "held back, held for the hands of rain," indicating a release of pent-up emotions and a rebirth of sorts.⁴

4. Capable of complex thoughts and emotions: Chopin portrays Mrs. Mallard as a woman with a rich inner life. When she contemplates her future without her husband, she experiences a range of contradictory emotions, including joy, fear, and guilt. This suggests that she is capable of deep introspection and wrestles with complex emotions.

DISCUSSION

Overall, the psycholinguistic descriptions of the characters in "The Story of an Hour" reveal a complex inner world filled with conflicted emotions and desires, as Mrs. Mallard navigates societal expectations and her own personal aspirations. Moreover, the story highlights how Louise's psyche changes after hearing the news. At first, she is devastated, but as time progresses, her thoughts undergo a metamorphosis. One of the most notable examples of this is when Louise reflects on her newfound independence, Chopin's language mirrors this liberation as words like "free," "body," and "soul" encircles her thoughts.⁴ These words convey a sense of power that Louise has never felt before.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Chopin illustrates the importance of language and psychology in the "Story of an Hour." The story is an exemplar of how authors can use language to represent the mental state of their characters. Chopin's use of language is instrumental in conveying Louise's emotional state and her psychological response to the events that unfold. It is through the careful manipulation of language that Chopin can communicate Louise's emotions to the reader, allowing them to join her on her emotional journey.

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